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BUSINESS ENGLISH:
THE FUNDAMENTAL TOOL FOR THE INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS

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Today the most widespread language in the world by the number of native speakers is Chinese, however, it's not common to hear it outside of Chinese communities. Simultaneously, English itself breaks another kind of record. It will be difficult to estimate the exact number of English speakers but approximately it equals 350 million native speakers and over 400 million users. However, the significance of English may not be assumed just based on the number of people who speak it.

In order to demonstrate the real advantage in comparison with Chinese, it is necessary to pay attention to the following: English is the main language of news, information exchange, business and administration in the world, where a separate place belongs to business English, a form of this language which especially suits the international trade, commerce and finance. Since the middle of the last century, it has been taking leading positions in a business environment.

Taking into account that domestic businesses nowadays try to enter the European and world markets, diversifying their activities abroad, its knowledge is becoming a prerequisite for the successful development of both business in general and any person's career, providing employees with higher wages and possibilities of business trips. At the moment it is hard to imagine the successful development of an organization that does not cooperate with foreign entities and clients. Therefore, there are many options for the company's development - from expanding the number of partners and cooperation with foreign companies to opening branches in other countries. And there is no doubt that it is going to be easier to promote one's business and conquer markets when key staff in there can use English in their work.

For the leader English could present the next benefits: an ability to analyze the western market independently, learn successful business models and then introduce modern trends in his company, allow to understand partners better and run the business without using the help of translators, developing good contacts or expressing one's ideas and intentions accurately using correct grammatical structures and vocabulary in statements, strengthen

the ability to engage the investors' and partners' right in your product, and defend your development independently and present any project directly.

In the context of the country, the economic transition from industrial production to an innovative economy requires the adult population with excellent English skills which can cooperate with foreign companies and especially people who are capable of using a special business vocabulary, a specific form of oral and written speech, and have an understanding the structure of negotiations, writing business letters, and the correct using of terms in speech as well as knowing how to use a conceptual apparatus in a sphere of law, finance, logistics, human resources, etc., keeping in mind at the same time that the same terms can have various meaning in different states. That's why in the case of dealing with interstate affairs it is important not only to learn the basics of ordinary English but also to master a more difficult version of it. It should be noted, that the knowledge of English will be of great benefit not only in business but also in the social sphere as well.

So, it becomes more obvious every year that the fruitfulness of business communication is impossible without a confident knowledge of the Business English language and its correct use.